

ONE DISEASE MULTIPLE DISGUISES: SUBDURAL EMPYEMA, CEREBRAL VENOUS THROMBOSIS, AND MIXED AUTOIMMUNE HEMOLYTIC ANEMIA UNMASKING SYSTEMIC LUPUS ERYTHEMATOSUS - A RARE CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Central Nervous System (CNS) infections in Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE) are a known risk; however, subdural empyema represents an exceptionally rare and life-threatening intracranial infection, particularly as an initial presentation of the disease. Mixed Autoimmune Hemolytic Anemia (AIHA), defined by the presence of both warm and cold antibodies against the patient's own erythrocytes, is a rare hematological entity. We report a case of a 19-year-old female who presented with a one-month history of severe headache, blurring of vision, and intermittent fever. Although she was initially stable, her clinical course deteriorated on the second day of admission with the onset of focal seizures affecting the left upper limb. Preliminary investigations revealed severe anemia (Hemoglobin 3.3 g/dL) and thrombocytopenia. A peripheral blood smear demonstrated anisopoikilocytosis and schistocytes. Biochemical markers indicated hemolysis with elevated lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) levels (1745 U/L) and indirect hyperbilirubinemia. Immunological evaluation confirmed mixed AIHA with a positive monospecific Direct Antiglobulin Test (DAT) for both IgG and C3. Further serology was reactive for ANA and anti-dsDNA, confirming a diagnosis of SLE. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) of the brain identified a subdural empyema in the left frontoparietal region accompanied by dural venous sinus thrombosis. The patient was managed aggressively with broad-spectrum intravenous antibiotics, anticoagulation, and pulse steroid therapy, resulting in significant clinical improvement. This case highlights the diagnostic complexity of SLE when it presents simultaneously with severe autoimmune cytopenias and rare intracranial infections.

KEYWORDS: Systemic Lupus Erythematosus, Subdural Empyema, Autoimmune Hemolytic Anemia, Neuro-lupus, Mixed AIHA.

INTRODUCTION

Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE) is a complex autoimmune disease distinguished by its tendency to involve multiple organ systems and its production of a broad spectrum of autoantibodies.^[1] Among the hematologic manifestations, Autoimmune Hemolytic Anemia (AIHA) is relatively common; however, the mixed variant—comprising elements of both Warm AIHA and Cold Agglutinin Disease—is a rare finding.^[2] Involvement of the Central Nervous System (CNS) is observed in approximately 25–75% of SLE cases, typically presenting as cognitive dysfunction, seizures, psychosis, or cerebrovascular events.^[3] Intracranial infections, such as subdural empyema, are exceedingly

uncommon in this demographic and are generally attributed to the immunosuppressed state inherent to the disease or its treatment.^[4] We present a rare case of a young female newly diagnosed with SLE who presented with a triad of Mixed AIHA, Subdural Empyema, and Cerebral Venous Thrombosis.

CASE REPORT

A 19-year-old female presented to our hospital with chief complaints of a severe headache persisting for one month and intermittent fever for three days. The patient had been in her usual state of health until the onset of the headache, which was insidious, holocranial, and severe in intensity. She described the pain as radiating to the

neck and noted associated symptoms including blurring of vision, nausea, and non-projectile vomiting. She also reported alopecia but denied oral ulcers, arthralgia or rashes. Her obstetric history was significant for one missed abortion at 58 days of gestation and a history of ectopic pregnancy, which had been managed via laparoscopic salpingectomy. There was no other significant medical or surgical history reported.

On general physical examination, the patient was conscious, cooperative, and oriented to time, place, and person. She was moderately built. Notable findings included pallor and icterus. There was no evidence of generalized lymphadenopathy or pedal edema. The patient was hemodynamically stable at admission. Initial neurological assessment revealed no signs of meningeal irritation and no focal neurological deficits. Cardiovascular, respiratory, and abdominal examinations were unremarkable.

On the second day of hospitalization, the patient developed a single episode of focal seizure characterized by involvement of the left upper limb. This clinical deterioration prompted immediate re-evaluation and further diagnostic imaging.

Preliminary blood investigations revealed severe anemia with a hemoglobin level of 3.3 g/dL and significant thrombocytopenia (platelet count: 31,000/ μ L). The total leukocyte count remained within normal limits. Examination of the peripheral blood smear showed anisopoikilocytosis, polychromatophils, and the presence of schistocytes. The reticulocyte count was elevated at 1.3%. Biochemical markers for hemolysis were strongly positive. Serum Lactate Dehydrogenase (LDH) was markedly elevated at 1745 U/L. Liver function tests demonstrated hyperbilirubinemia (Total Bilirubin: 3.9 mg/dL) with a predominance of the indirect fraction

(Indirect Bilirubin: 2.7 mg/dL). Liver enzymes were otherwise normal.

Blood grouping and typing presented technical difficulties due to significant auto-agglutination. A baseline Coombs test was positive. The patient was subjected to a Mono-specific Direct Antiglobulin Test (DAT), Indirect Antiglobulin Test (IAT), and antibody screening.

DAT: Positive for both Anti-IgG and Anti-C3 antibodies.

IAT: Positive (1+)

Auto Control: Strongly reactive (4+) at 4°C. These findings confirmed the diagnosis of Mixed AIHA (combined warm and cold type).

Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (ESR) was elevated at 120 mm/hr, and C-Reactive Protein (CRP) was 10 mg/dL. On evaluation for Connective Tissue Disorders, The Antinuclear Antibody (ANA) test was reactive (4+). Further profiling revealed low complement levels (C3: 0.341, C4: <0.067) and positivity for Anti-Nucleosome and Anti-dsDNA antibodies, fulfilling the diagnostic criteria for Systemic Lupus Erythematosus. Antiphospholipid antibody testing could not be performed.

Renal function tests, serum calcium (8.5 mg/dL), and thyroid profile (Free T3, Free T4, TSH) were within normal limits. Urinalysis indicated proteinuria of 660 mg/day. Chest X-ray & ECG was normal. Ultrasound Abdomen revealed minimal free fluid in the Pouch of Douglas. MRI of the Brain demonstrated features suggestive of a subdural empyema in the left frontoparietal region with minimal midline shift and concurrent dural venous sinus thrombosis.

Table 1: Hematological Parameters at time of admission and discharge.

Parameter	On admission	At discharge
Hemoglobin	3.3 g/dL	10.0 g/dL
MCV	137 fL	121.2 fL
RBC Count	0.78 x 10 ⁶ / μ L	2.78 10 ⁶ / μ L
Total Leukocyte Count	10,500 / μ L	8,100 / μ L
Platelet count	31,000 / μ L	129,000 / μ L

Table 2: Liver Function Tests.

Total Bilirubin	Indirect Bilirubin	Direct Bilirubin	Albumin	Globulin	A/G Ratio
3.9 mg/dL	2.7 mg/dL	1.2 mg/dL	3.9 g/dL	2.41 g/dL	1.6:1

Table 3: Immunological Parameters.

Test	Result	Reference Range
Serum LDH	1745 U/L	140-280 U/L
Serum C3	0.341 g/L	0.8 to 1.8 g/L
Serum C4	Less than 0.067 g/L	0.10-0.40 g/L
ANA	4+	
Anti-ds DNA	14 U/mL	<6
Coombs Test (Direct)	Positive (3+); Anti-C3d (3+); Anti-IgG (2+)	

Indirect Coombs (IAT)	Positive (1+)	
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The subdural empyema was managed with broad-spectrum intravenous antibiotics. For the cerebral venous thrombosis, the patient was heparinized. To address the autoimmune cytopenias and SLE flare, she was started on pulse steroid therapy. Intravenous Methyl Prednisolone 1 g/day for 3 days which was subsequently switched over to oral Prednisolone (1 mg/kg/day), and was gradually tapered.

Supportive measures and continuous neurological monitoring were maintained throughout her stay. The patient demonstrated a significant clinical response, with resolution of the headache, cessation of seizures, and normalization of hemoglobin levels. She was discharged in stable condition with instructions for regular follow-up.

DISCUSSION

Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE) is a protean autoimmune disorder capable of affecting virtually any organ system. Hematological abnormalities are among the most frequent clinical manifestations, occurring in approximately 50–75% of patients.^[1] While anemia of chronic disease is the most common form, Autoimmune Hemolytic Anemia (AIHA) occurs in 10–20% of cases.^[5]

The presentation of Mixed AIHA in this patient—defined by the presence of both warm-reactive IgG and cold-reactive IgM autoantibodies—is a distinct rarity. Mixed AIHA accounts for less than 10% of all AIHA cases and is often associated with a more severe clinical course and resistance to therapy compared to the isolated warm or cold subtypes.^[2, 6] The simultaneous presence of Anti-IgG and Anti-C3 on the Direct Antiglobulin Test (DAT), alongside the serological confirmation of SLE (ANA and Anti-dsDNA positivity), underscores the intense autoimmune dysregulation present at diagnosis.

The most critical aspect of this case was the neurological presentation. Neuropsychiatric SLE (NPSLE) can manifest in up to 95% of patients, with seizures and headaches being common features.^[3] However, distinguishing primary NPSLE from secondary CNS complications, particularly infections, is a major diagnostic dilemma. Subdural empyema is an intracranial collection of pus between the dura mater and the arachnoid mater. It is a medical emergency with a mortality rate of approximately 13% even in the modern era.^[7] In the context of SLE, subdural empyema is exceptionally rare. It typically arises from the contiguous spread of infection (e.g., sinusitis, otitis media) or via hematogenous seeding.^[8] In our patient, the absence of a clear primary infectious focus suggests a possible cryptic source or hematogenous spread facilitated by the immune dysregulation inherent to SLE.

The MRI Brain also revealed Cerebral Venous Thrombosis (CVT). CVT is a recognized but infrequent complication of SLE, with a reported prevalence of less

than 1%.^[9] The pathogenesis is likely multifactorial, involving the hypercoagulable state associated with active inflammation and potentially the presence of antiphospholipid antibodies.^[1, 9]

The management of this patient required a delicate balance between immunosuppression and antimicrobial therapy. High-dose corticosteroids are the cornerstone of treatment for acute hematologic and neurologic lupus flares.^[1, 3] However, the presence of a subdural empyema necessitated aggressive antibiotic coverage to prevent the catastrophic spread of infection, which could be exacerbated by steroids. The successful outcome in this case validates the combined approach of pulse corticosteroids to halt hemolysis and broad-spectrum antibiotics to treat the empyema.^[4]

CONCLUSION

This case report documents an extremely rare triad of Mixed Autoimmune Hemolytic Anemia, Subdural Empyema and Cerebral Venous Thrombosis as the initial presentation of Systemic Lupus Erythematosus. It serves as a critical reminder that neurological symptoms in SLE should not be reflexively attributed to lupus cerebritis. A high index of suspicion for intracranial infection is mandatory, especially when clinical features are atypical or severe. The successful resolution of this case highlights the importance of early neuroimaging and a coordinated, multidisciplinary approach involving Rheumatology and Neurology.

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REFERENCES

- Loscalzo J, Fauci A, Kasper D, Hauser S, Longo D, Jameson J. Harrison's Principles of Internal Medicine. 21st ed. McGraw Hill; 2022. Chapter 356, Systemic Lupus Erythematosus.
- Hill A, Hill QA. Autoimmune hemolytic anemia. *Hematology Am Soc Hematol Educ Program*, 2018; 2018(1): 382-389.
- Ralston S, Penman I, Strachan M, Hobson R. Davidson's Principles and Practice of Medicine. 24th ed. Elsevier; 2022. Chapter 25, Rheumatology and Bone Disease.
- Bortoluzzi A, Scirè CA, Govoni M. Central Nervous System Involvement in Systemic Lupus Erythematosus. *Best Pract Res Clin Rheumatol*, 2018; 32(5): 648-660.
- Jeffries M, Hamadeh F, Aberle T, et al. Haemolytic anaemia in a multi-ethnic cohort of systemic lupus erythematosus patients: clinical associations and outcomes. *Lupus*, 2008; 17(8): 739-743.
- Sokol RJ, Hewitt S, Stamps BK. Autoimmune haemolysis: an 18-year study of 865 cases referred

- to a regional transfusion centre. *Br Med J (Clin Res Ed)*, 1981; 282(6281): 2023-2027.
7. French H, Pearl M, Reginato A. Subdural empyema in a patient with systemic lupus erythematosus: A case report and review of the literature. *Lupus*, 2013; 22: 96-99.
 8. Nathoo N, Nadvi SS, van Dellen JR. Intracranial subdural empyemas in the era of computed tomography: a review of 699 cases. *Neurosurgery*, 1999; 44(3): 529-535.
 9. Wang L, Zhou J, Song Y, et al. Cerebral venous thrombosis in systemic lupus erythematosus: a single center experience in China. *J Clin Neurosci*, 2019; 63: 108-113.
 10. Mote S, Lokesh L, Dutta A, Danasekaran V. Auto Immune Mixed Haemolytic anaemia: A rare presentation of SLE. *Int J Adv Med*, 2019; 6: 954-8.